

MOFs and nanozymes in electrochemical environmental (bio)sensing: recent advances and field translation

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ABSTRACT

Electrochemical (bio)sensing is increasingly positioned as a practical complement to laboratory-based analytical methodologies for environmental monitoring, especially where high-frequency, on-site measurements are required. In this context, metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) and nanozymes have rapidly gained wide interest to reshape the electrode not just as a passive conductor, but as a versatile interface. MOFs' tunable porosity and high-density adsorption sites can be coupled with enzyme-mimetic catalysis for signal amplification. Given the exponential expansion of the literature on this topic, this review aims to provide a snapshot of the advances published during the last year, 2025, focusing on (bio)sensing for the detection of major contaminant classes, including per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), heavy metals, antibiotics, and microplastics. Recurrent design logics emerged, such as porous layers that increase local analyte levels at the electrode interface, redox-active frameworks that provide intrinsic transduction, and nanozyme-driven amplification schemes that translate weak binding events or trace-level concentrations into measurable signals. Moreover, this report highlights how current strategies are being increasingly challenged in environmental-matrix validation to achieve field-ready platforms.

1. Introduction

The global propagation of emerging contaminants across water systems, soils, and food chains necessitates the rapid development of analytical methodologies that prioritize sensitivity and decentralization. Environmental monitoring, particularly in water matrices, is increasingly challenged by persistent, non-biodegradable pollutants, such as PFAS, heavy metal ions, microplastics, antibiotics (leading to antimicrobial resistance) and many other chemical compounds [1]. Each of these pollutants poses distinct environmental and health-related threats, ranging from immunosuppression, neurological damage, cancer, antimicrobial-resistant infections, to the complete invasion of ecosystems with microplastics and additives [2–4]. Indeed, the mid-2020s are experiencing a rapidly evolving regulatory landscape regarding environmental contaminants. Yet, the analytical methods traditionally applied to these analytes are tied to laboratory-bound technologies and require high operating costs, complex sample preparation, expert personnel, and instrumentation that prohibit real-time, on-site deployment. In this context, electrochemical sensors offer a practical solution

to the challenges of decentralized monitoring and are characterized by high selectivity and sensitivity, rapid response time, minimal power consumption, and inexpensive, portable instrumentation, often without sacrificing analytical performance [5]. The latter is often enhanced by modifying the physical electrode surface with functional materials capable of providing high surface area, maximizing active sites and electron transfer kinetics and/or making the electrode sensitive and selective against specific analytes. This aspect becomes increasingly more important as many environmental contaminants of concern are either electroinactive or only weakly electroactive, and often occur at ultra-trace levels in complex matrices that promote electrode fouling [6, 7].

Metal-organic frameworks (MOFs) and enzyme-mimicking nano-materials (nanozymes) have emerged as two of the most versatile classes of such electrode modifiers, capable of increasing the analytical performances enough to cover the sensitivities required for many environmental monitoring applications [8]. MOFs are a relatively young branch of material chemistry. They emerged in the 1990s from the meeting point of coordination chemistry and crystal engineering and are

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porous coordination polymers characterized by an “infinite” network of metal-containing units (nodes or clusters) interconnected by multitopic organic ligands [9]. The results are periodic networks with enormous internal surface areas and tunable pore sizes. Likewise, their chemistry can also be tuned: metal centers can be swapped and ligands can be functionalized with acidic, basic, redox-active, or fluorophilic groups [10–12].

MOFs' trajectory has been steep. Early work primarily explored these materials for gas adsorption [13]. Two decades later, MOFs are being proposed for numerous practical uses, including hydrogen storage, carbon capture, catalysis, drug delivery, and increasingly also sensing and energy conversion [11,14]. This expansion was recently recognized in October 2025, when the Royal Swedish Academy of Sciences awarded the Nobel Prize in Chemistry to Susumu Kitagawa, Richard Robson, and Omar M. Yaghi “for the development of metal-organic frameworks”. This highlighted how MOFs moved from elegant crystal structures to application-oriented materials, with sensing frequently cited among the potential applications not only for their porosity, but also for their particular modularity. By selecting a metal node with desired redox properties, pairing it with a ligand bearing specific functional groups, tuning pore sizes and shape, and introducing hierarchical structure or flexibility, researchers can obtain materials that act as more than passive supports [15]. They can be engineered to recognize analytes through host-guest interactions, to catalyze redox reactions, or to interface efficiently with electrodes [12]. In this context, the literature often emphasizes three main advantages of MOFs in sensing: (i) extremely high surface area that enhances analyte preconcentration; (ii) chemically addressable internal surfaces that can host recognition sites, functional ligands, or immobilized biomolecules; and (iii) the possibility to couple these features to conductivity, either intrinsically or *via* composites.

Another recent story is that of nanozymes, with two initial milestones in 2004 by Scrimin and co-workers [16,17] and then in 2007 when Yan's group noticed that Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles could exhibit peroxidase-mimicking properties [18]. Over the following decade, a wide number of nanomaterials were reported to exhibit enzyme-like activity, including metal oxides (e.g., Fe₃O₄, CeO₂, MnO₂), metal nanoparticles (Au, Pt, Pd), Prussian blue analogues, and carbon-based materials [19]. Even more interesting appear to be single-atom nanozymes (SAzymes), based on isolated metal atoms (e.g., Fe, Co, Cu) anchored on supports like nitrogen-doped carbon, resulting in catalytic turnovers capable of reaching (or exceeding) those of natural enzymes [17,20]. Unlike the latter, which rely on delicate and expensive protein structures that are prone to denaturation and difficult to store in the field, nanozymes offer high stability in harsh environmental conditions (e.g., pH, salinity, temperature), lower production costs, and stable storage [21]. Increased interest in nanozymes has also been prompted by IUPAC in 2022, when nanozymes were recognized as one of the “top ten emerging technologies in chemistry” [22].

Electrochemical sensing recently exploited the advantages of these materials to overcome some of the limitations of bare electrodes, which are often insufficient for complex, non-electroactive contaminants, lack selectivity, and are prone to fouling [23]. Initially, MOFs served as “high-surface-area modifiers” (for instance, to preconcentrate analytes near the electrode surface), but their poor intrinsic conductivity often limited sensitivity. Then, conductive MOFs able to participate in the redox cycle began to be explored, and the analytical exploitation of techniques based on changes in charge transfer resistance (*i.e.*, electrochemical impedance spectroscopy) or capacitive sensing appeared [24]. Now, MOFs are used as electrode substrates, nanocarriers for signal reporters, electrocatalysts, and electroactive labels [12].

An advancement is given by a composite approach that combines the high porosity and tunable chemistry of MOFs with the conductivity of carbon nanostructures (e.g., graphene, carbon nanotubes) or conductive polymers, while embedding nanozymes within the pores to achieve catalytic activity for signal amplification [25,26]. Nowadays, MOF-based nanozymes can act as multiple enzyme-like catalysts,

including peroxidase, laccase, carbonic anhydrase, superoxide dismutase, methane monooxygenase, and lipase, as well as multienzyme systems [8,21,27].

Several review papers have catalogued and summarized different applications of MOF- and nanozyme-based platforms over the years across diverse areas, including cancer therapy and detection [28–30], virus detection [31], electrochemical glucose sensors [32], and the detection of food and environmental pollutants [33,34], underscoring the versatility of these materials.

In particular, research around electrochemical sensors coupled with MOFs and/or nanozymes for environmental monitoring has dramatically expanded over the last decade. Fig. 1 shows how the number of publications has risen from only a few reports 10 years ago to well above one hundred in 2025. Particularly, the number of publications for each year was fitted with an exponential function to make this growth particularly clear, indicating that activity in this niche is not just increasing, but accelerating, as more researchers turn to MOF- and nanozyme-based architectures to tackle the pressing environmental monitoring requirements mentioned.

The role of MOFs and nanozymes in electrochemical sensing of environmental contaminants can be summarized considering their chemical features: (i) the ordered porous architectures and high surface area of MOF that enable the preconcentration of the pollutants; (ii) the modular design of MOFs that allows precise control over pore architecture and functional groups, facilitating size- and chemistry-dependent selective recognition/capturing of molecules. This is particularly interesting for pollutants known as “forever chemicals”, such as PFAS or microplastics. For instance, PFAS could be selectively captured and preconcentrated onto MOF-nanostructures by a combination of electrostatic interactions between anionic PFAS head groups and positively charged metal nodes, hydrogen bonding with coordinated ligands, and hydrophobic or fluorophilic interactions with the perfluorinated alkyl chains, allowing selective enrichment and sensing of different PFAS classes. Indeed, the possibility of a selective recognition and preconcentration offered by MOFs is particularly interesting for these pollutants, because antibodies against PFAS can be challenging to produce, as PFAS may not be (sufficiently) immunogenic to elicit a strong immune response [35]. Furthermore, natural bioreceptors are often very sensitive to harsh environmental conditions, such as pH levels and organic solvents, which may be present in real samples or required for sensor regeneration. In this context, synthetic receptors such as molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs) coupled to electrochemical sensors provide an attractive and cheaper alternative to natural bioreceptors and have recently been reported in the literature for the detection of PFAS. However, compared with MIPs, MOFs could provide structurally uniform and accessible recognition environments.

Fig. 1. The number of papers published in the last ten years has grown following an exponential trend. The literature was screened using the following keywords and Boolean operators: “*electrochemical AND sensor AND (MOFs OR nanozymes) AND environmental*” (SciFinder, November 2025).

Furthermore, MOF-based sensing exhibits superior chemical stability and operational robustness in complex water matrices when compared with aptamers (nucleic acid synthetic receptors), which are vulnerable to degradation and matrix interference. Indeed, MOFs and MOF-based nanozymes can also be affected by fluctuating pH and biofouling. In this case, a postsynthetic modification with protective groups, as well as a rational synthesis – using selected metal ions (*i.e.*, Fe³⁺, Zr⁴⁺) or nitrogen-donor ligands (*i.e.*, tetrazolates, imidazolates, triazolates, and pyrazolates) [36] – might produce MOFs that are stable in extreme environments. Moreover, smart structures such as MOF-on-MOF [36] and hollow-structured MOFs [37–39] are also claimed to provide valuable assistance for environmental complex matrices.

Similar considerations are also valid for another important class of forever chemicals, *i.e.*, microplastics; in this case, hydrophobic and π - π interactions with aromatic moieties could be used for the preconcentration/sensing of microplastics using MOFs.

Therefore, in this review paper the discussion is organized around four major contaminant classes: (i) per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances, (ii) heavy metals, (iii) micro- and nanoplastics, and (iv) antibiotics, all chosen as they present pressing regulatory and public health concerns, as well as illustrate distinct sensing challenges. Moreover, it intends to summarize the innovative approaches and current performance benchmarks achieved with electrochemical sensors that utilize MOFs, nanozymes, or hybrid MOF-nanozyme platforms, with scope deliberately confined to technological innovations and sensor designs published during the year 2025. This temporal restriction aims to provide a “snapshot” of the field at an inflection point, one in which laboratory demonstrations are beginning to evolve into application-centered devices challenged in real-world monitoring scenarios.

2. MOFs/nanozymes-enhanced PFAS sensing

Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) occupy an important place within the concern around contemporary environmental and public health. Monitoring efforts towards these synthetic “forever chemicals” encounter a stubborn paradox in modern environmental analysis: the very chemical stability that renders the carbon-fluorine (C–F) bond invaluable for industrial applications, simultaneously makes these molecules exceptionally persistent across water, soil, biota, and even the human bloodstream [40]. Consequently, regulatory bodies, such as the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA), have established extremely stringent maximum contaminant levels for key compounds like perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA) and perfluorooctanesulfonic acid (PFOS) at 4.0 ppt [41]. Indeed, meeting this low detection requirement poses a great challenge for environmental monitoring.

The analytical gold standard, performed by skilled personnel through complex protocols, is liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) [42]. Such a technique indeed offers high precision and sensitivity, but is chained to costly equipment, complex protocols, trained staff, and cumbersome sample preparation. Recent critical reviews by Gondhiya *et al.* [43] and Dube *et al.* [44] argue that the logistical footprint of mass spectrometry is rapidly becoming incompatible with the urgent need for high-frequency, decentralized environmental monitoring. The limitation appears to be no longer sensitivity, but accessibility.

This has driven researchers to explore electrochemical sensors, which offer a series of advantages, including the ability to interface directly with digital and/or continuous monitoring systems. These platforms measure molecular recognition and electron transfer at electrode surfaces, opening a path toward decentralized or even wearable PFAS detection [45]. While electrochemical sensors easily reach the sensitivities required for environmental PFAS levels and regulatory guidelines, a critical bottleneck still remains: conventional electrodes struggle to differentiate similar PFAS congeners (*e.g.*, PFOA vs. PFOS), especially in complex matrices [35,46]. Moreover, the challenge also lies in PFAS's non- or weak electroactive nature, which pushes the need

for clever surface engineering, redox-active mediators, or synthetic receptors to detect them.

The vast majority of electrochemical sensors for PFAS reported in the recent literature rely on molecularly imprinted polymers (MIPs), namely synthetic recognition materials that exploit template-specific cavities created within a polymeric matrix during an imprinting process [35,47]. These cavities are complementary in morphology, size, and functional group configuration to the target molecule, thus working as artificial receptors as alternatives to biomolecular recognition elements like enzymes or antibodies [48]. However, in 2025, the literature has been showing a shift from materials that merely adsorb PFAS, like MIPs, toward nanostructures designed to recognize these compounds through specific host-guest interactions. In this context, MOFs offer good binding capabilities through mechanisms that include electrostatic interactions (with anionic PFAS species), hydrogen bonding, and fluorophilic F–F interactions facilitated by fluorinated linkers or organic backbones (Table 1). Meanwhile, nanozyme catalysis can amplify redox signals or transduce adsorption events into measurable signals, bypassing PFAS's weak electroactivity. PFAS adsorption at the MOFs interface modulates signal amplification because any electrochemical response (impedance, capacitance, faradaic current) scales with surface coverage. In EIS-focused PFAS sensors, MOFs amplify signals by modulating interfacial resistance and capacitance through PFAS adsorption, whereas in amperometric sensors, nanozymes provide catalytic amplification with MOFs enhancing local PFAS enrichment and mass transport control. PFAS detection strategy can be improved by combining MIPs with MOFs, as demonstrated by Cheng and co-workers [49]. More in details, in their paper, they integrate dual-functional monomers (dopamine and *ortho*-phenylenediamine) onto a supporting scaffold composed of Al/Co-based MOFs and reduced graphene oxide (rGO) on a glassy carbon electrode (GCE) (Fig. 2a). While the rGO enhances electron transfer kinetics, the MOF offers a high-surface area for the MIP layer that presents cavities tailored to perfluorooctanoic acid (PFOA). Quantum chemical calculations supported the stronger affinity of the dual-monomer approach when compared to the single-monomer MIPs often encountered in the literature. The authors report a limit of detection (LOD) of 5 pM and recoveries in the range 94–107% in river water samples. Nevertheless, short-chain PFAS (*e.g.*, perfluorobutanoic acid and perfluorohexanoic acid) analogues remain problematic for selectivity.

The synergy of MOFs and nanozymes appears even more interesting. MOFs containing redox-active metal clusters can exhibit enzyme-like catalytic activity [50]. Su *et al.* [51] employed TiO₂ nanochannels modified with cerium-based MOFs (Ce-MOFs), which act as nanozymes that mimic peroxidase activity, and a polyelectrolyte multilayer made of poly(diallyldimethylammonium) and poly(styrenesulfonate) (PDDA/PSS) to regulate the nanochannel's surface (Fig. 2b). The ionic current measured is correlated to the nanozyme-catalyzed redox reaction of 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB). However, the resulting catalytic activity alone was not sufficient for trace detection of PFAS. Thus, by playing with the microenvironment, and especially with surface charge and hydrophobicity of the nanochannels, the authors managed to concentrate PFOA molecules near the Ce-MOF active sites, achieving signal amplification that allowed for a LOD of 78 pM. In particular, the sensing mechanism is explained considering that PFOA effectively displaces PSS in PDDA/PSS, thereby triggering a distinct surface structure. PDDA/PFOA complexes exhibit both electrostatic and stronger hydrophobic interactions, which arise between the pyrrolidine rings of PDDA and the perfluorinated chains of PFOA. The overall stability of PDDA/PFOA complexes surpasses that of PDDA/PSS complexes. I–V curves were recorded in 1 μ M KCl solution containing 1 mM TMB and 10 mM H₂O₂. After the displacement of PSS by PFOA, the peroxidase-mimicking activity of Ce-MOF, combined with the hydrophobic effect induced by the resulting nanochannels, facilitates the generation and subsequent adsorption of oxTMB within the nanochannels. This process alters the surface charge of the nanochannels

Table 1

Summary of sensing mechanisms and analytical performances of 2025-reported PFAS sensors utilizing MOFs and/or nanozymes.

Target	Primary MOF/nanozyme/material	Electrode material	Key mechanism	LOD	Dynamic range	RSD (reproducibility)	Real samples tested (recovery)	Ref.
PFOA	Dual-monomer MIP/Al/Co-MOFs/rGO	GCE	PFOA is recognized by the imprinted <i>o</i> -PD and DA film, blocking $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{3-/4-}$ access to the conductive MOF/rGO modified electrode.	5 pM	10 pM – 100 nM	7.3%	River water, tap water, mineral water (94-107%)	[49]
PFOA, PFOS	Cu-HHTP	ITO	Impedimetric sensor based on a conductive 2D MOF. Adsorption of PFAS leads to an increase in channel conductance.	5 fM	n.d.	n.a.	Drinking water	[50]
PFOA	Ce-MOF/PDDA/PSS/TiNM	TiNM	PFOA-mediated displacement of PSS renders the nanochannels hydrophobic, enhancing adsorption of charged oxTMB and suppressing peroxidase-like activity of Ce-MOF. Result: altered ion transport.	78 pM	0.25 nM – 1 mM	1.2%	Landfill leachate (101-103%)	[51]
PFOA	F-Cu-NH ₂ BDC	GCE	Exploits MOF's intrinsic $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Cu}^+$ redox signal and F-F interactions to induce PFOA self-aggregation, blocking electroactive sites and reducing signal.	3.54 pM	5 pM – 500 μM	3.5%	Commercial drinking water (96-109%)	[52]

Cu-HHTP: copper hexahydroxy triphenylene; DA: dopamine; F-Cu-NH₂BDC: fluorine-copper-2-amino-terephthalic acid; GCE: glassy carbon electrode; ITO: indium-tin oxide; LOD: limit of detection; MOF: metal organic framework; n.a.: not available; *o*-PD: *ortho*-phenylenediamine; oxTMB: oxidized 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine; PDDA: poly(diallyldimethylammonium); PFOA: perfluorooctanoic acid; PFOS: perfluorooctanesulfonic acid; PSS: poly(styrenesulfonate); rGO: reduced graphene oxide; RSD: relative standard deviation; TiNM: TiO₂ nanochannels membranes.

Fig. 2. PFAS sensing schemes using electrochemical sensors based on MOFs and/or nanozymes. (a) PFOA signal-off detection with a MIP layer based on dopamine and *o*-phenylenediamine on MOF/rGO/GCE. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [49]. (b) PFOA induces a hydrophilic-to-hydrophobic wettability switching mechanism, leading to detectable altered ion transport dynamics within the TiO₂ nanochannel membranes modified with a Ce-based MOF with peroxidase-like activity in the presence of 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB). Reprinted with permission from Ref. [51]. (c) PFOA detection by exploiting F-F interactions between a rationally designed fluorine-functionalized Cu-MOF and PFOA on GCE; signal-off mechanism based on $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Cu}^+$ redox reaction monitored by square-wave voltammetry. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [52].

(oxTMB being positively charged), leading to significant variations in transmembrane ion flux. Molecular dynamics (MD) simulations were performed to quantify the binding energy and binding mode of oxTMB with PSS and PFOA (the outermost molecules of the hydrophobic nanochannels). The binding energy under hydrophobic conditions increases, confirming the superior thermodynamic stability of oxTMB-PFOA complexes but also mechanistically explaining the enhanced interfacial effects. The combined steric hindrance and charge redistribution intensify ion current modulation, laying the foundation

for signal amplification strategies. Moreover, the authors claim that the sensor could be reused through simple salt-wash regeneration and that it could discriminate among PFAS with different chain lengths.

Another interesting use of MOFs is to develop sensing architectures that do not require exogenous redox probes to simplify the whole detection scheme. For instance, focusing again on the detection of PFOA, Zheng and colleagues [52] exploited the intrinsic redox signal of an electroactive fluorine-functionalized copper-amine MOF material immobilized on a GCE (Fig. 2c). In particular, the MOF material

(copper-2-amino-terephthalic acid) was post-modified using a Schiff base reaction with 2,3,5,6-tetrafluoroterephthalaldehyde (TFTA) to introduce fluorine-rich functionalities, on the basis of a hydrophobic gating strategy. The sensor relied (i) on the inherent $\text{Cu}^{2+}/\text{Cu}^+$ redox reaction and (ii) on F-F interactions among PFOA molecules and between PFOA and the MOF's fluorine groups to induce the self-aggregation of PFOA on the MOF surface. This self-aggregation led to a concentration-dependent blocking mechanism of the Cu electroactive sites, which inhibited electron transfer between the Cu^{2+} sites and the electrolyte. In addition, the use of a fluorine-functionalized linker creates a "fluorophilic" microenvironment, which both protects the MOF from hydrolysis due to the effect of the water-based environment, and selectively attracts analytes. The result is a reduction in the oxidation peak measured by square-wave voltammetry (SWV). The authors reported a LOD of 3.54 μM , an RSD of 3.53%, minimal interference from nonfluorinated compounds, and recoveries around 96-109% in spiked commercial drinking water.

3. Nanozymes/MOFs applied to heavy metal detection

Electrochemical sensors have long occupied a central position in the determination of heavy metals at trace levels in environmental samples [53–55]. Mercury-modified electrodes dominated the field for decades

thanks to their large cathodic window, reproducibility, and low background current. However, due to the toxicity and bioaccumulation risks related to mercury, the research has moved towards less-toxic alternatives [56–58]. Today, electrochemical heavy-metal sensors are entering a new phase driven by nanostructured materials that transform how electrodes interact with metal ions in complex environmental matrices. In particular, nanomaterials-based sensors have shown great promise in this field due to their large surface area, high catalytic efficiency, high surface reactivity, and strong adsorption capacity [59,60]. In recent years, a wide variety of nanomaterials such as metallic nanoparticles (NPs), carbon-based materials, and silicon-based materials have been used in the design of sensors for heavy metals determination [61,62]. Their inherent characteristics, which include high reactivity, large surface to volume-ratio, high degree of functionalization, and size-dependent properties, translate directly into superior sensitivity [63]. In addition, when these nanostructures are paired with catalytic nanomaterials, the resulting devices gain an additional layer of signal amplification and robustness, avoiding the fragility and storage constraints of biological enzymes while enabling lower detection limits and faster responses [64,65]. Different classes of nanomaterials, as doped carbon nanostructures, graphene derivatives, metallic nanoparticles, nanozymes, and metal-organic frameworks, offer distinct combinations of surface area, conductivity, and chemical functionality that directly

Fig. 3. MOF/nanozyme-based electrochemical sensors for heavy metal detection. (a) A dual-mode biosensor based on CRISPR/Cas12a and Pt/CeO₂ signal probes for the detection of Pb²⁺. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [67]. (b) Schematic illustration of the preparation of the UiO-66-NH₂(Zr)-GO nanocomposite-modified GCE and its application in the simultaneous sensing of multiple heavy-metal ions in aqueous solutions. Reprinted with permission from Ref. [68].

affect adsorption thermodynamics and electron-transfer kinetics [66].

Concerning nanozymes, many articles have been published in 2025 regarding the use of nanozymes for the determination of heavy metals. However, the vast majority of these papers focus on colorimetric sensing rather than electrochemical sensing. To the best of our knowledge, only a few catalytic nanomaterials with nanozyme-like behaviour were explicitly integrated into electrochemical sensors, as in the case of the work proposed by Meng *et al.* (2025) [67]. The study presents a DNAzyme-CRISPR dual-mode (electrochemical/colorimetric) biosensor enhanced by nanozyme catalytic amplification for Pb²⁺ detection (Fig. 3a). The authors integrate three synergistic mechanisms, that is, Pb²⁺-specific DNAzyme cleavage, CRISPR collateral amplification, and nanozyme-driven electrochemical catalysis, into a compact analytical platform designed for field deployment. CRISPR system (usually Cas12a or Cas13a) is a powerful, RNA-guided enzyme (a nuclease) from bacteria that acts like "molecular scissors" to cut DNA, functioning as both a gene-editing tool and a highly sensitive biosensor for detecting specific DNA sequences. The sensing mechanism is based on the use of a Pb²⁺-dependent DNAzyme which undergoes site-specific cleavage in the presence of the target ion. The cleavage product activates a CRISPR-Cas system, triggering collateral cleavage of reporter strands and generating a strong secondary amplification layer. This CRISPR output is then transduced electrochemically through a peroxidase-like nanozyme (Pt/CeO₂), which catalyzes the oxidation of a redox mediator, producing an amperometric signal. The authors report sub-nanomolar sensitivity, with a LOD in the picomolar range, which is below WHO and EPA regulatory limits for Pb²⁺ in drinking water. Real-sample application was performed using matrices like tap water, river water, and industrial wastewater, obtaining recoveries within the 92–108% range with relative standard deviations below 5%.

MOFs have rapidly become one of the most strategically important classes of materials for the electrochemical detection of heavy metals because they combine highly tunable chemistry with exceptional structural features that directly enhance electroanalytical performance. In latest years, significant progress has been made in leveraging MOFs and MOF-derived materials for the electrochemical detection of heavy metals in environmental and food matrices [69]. MOFs possess surface areas often exceeding 1000–6000 m²/g, far surpassing most metal oxides or carbon materials. Indeed, they provide dense populations of adsorption sites, dramatically increasing preconcentration efficiency. By concentrating metal ions (e.g., Pb²⁺, Cd²⁺, Hg²⁺, Cu²⁺, As³⁺) at the MOF-modified electrode surface before electrochemical reduction or oxidation, MOFs effectively lower detection limits. Additionally, their ordered pore networks facilitate rapid mass transport, improving response time and sensitivity [70,71].

In this context, Preusser *et al.* (2025) developed a novel hybrid nanocomposite based on a MOF and electroconductive cellulose nanocrystals (CNCs) for the simultaneous detection of Cd²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, and Hg²⁺ [72]. DUT-67 (a Zr-based MOF) was used to create a thin layer on a glassy carbon electrode *via* a drop-casting method. The electroconductive matrix was composed of poly(3,4-ethylenedioxythiophene) polystyrene sulfonate (PEDOT:PSS) and cellulose nanocrystals, which not only served as an effective template for the DUT-67 MOF, but also to enhance the electron transfer of the hybrid nanocomposites. Under optimized conditions for anodic stripping voltammetry measurements (solution pH, accumulation time, and accumulation potential), linear detection ranges of simultaneous detection of Cd²⁺, Pb²⁺, Cu²⁺, and Hg²⁺ were found to be in the ranges 20–163, 20–163, 20–84, and 20–112 µg L⁻¹, with detection limits of 2.5, 1.78, 0.226, and 0.294 µg L⁻¹, respectively, with no major interference effects from coexisting interfering ions. The developed sensor was applied to detect heavy metals in spiked aqueous samples (tap water, river water, lake water, and extracted soils), providing recoveries, in some cases, very close to 100%.

Portability remains a priority in field-based environmental monitoring. Wang and co-workers (2025) [73] addressed this by developing a

portable electrochemical sensor for the simultaneous quantification of Pb²⁺ and Cu²⁺ in aqueous environments. In their approach, a polyamide-amine dendrimers/Nickel MOF (PAMAM/Ni-MOFs) nanocomposite was synthesized and utilized as a sensing platform by modifying a GCE. Ni-MOFs exhibit an exceptional electrical conductivity. However, it is noteworthy that Ni-MOFs possess a limited number of imino-groups and demonstrate relatively weak coordination effects, indicating a need for the introduction of a greater number of active functional groups. This is achieved by coupling it with PAMAM, providing a high density of amino groups and a large specific surface area. The developed electrochemical sensor enables simultaneous detection of Pb²⁺ and Cu²⁺ using square-wave anodic stripping voltammetry (SWASV), showing a linear response within the range of 1–100 µg L⁻¹ and achieving detection limits (Pb²⁺: 1.21 µg L⁻¹; Cu²⁺: 0.77 µg L⁻¹) below the recommended thresholds for drinking water accepted by the World Health Organization (WHO).

In another approach, Kabir *et al.* (2025) [68] report the development of an electrochemical sensor based on a UiO-66-NH₂(Zr) (a functionalized variant of the classic UiO-66) MOF/graphene oxide (GO) nanocomposite for the simultaneous detection of multiple heavy metal ions in aqueous environments. Using a one-pot hydrothermal synthesis, MOFs and conductive GO-based materials were integrated into a single nanostructure *via* in situ growth of the UiO-66-NH₂(Zr) MOF on the GO matrix, resulting in the formation of a stable MOF/GO nanocomposite. This resulted in enhanced conductivity and increased number of effective reaction sites, as the amino groups on UiO-66-NH₂(Zr) porous materials could act as adsorption sites to capture heavy metal ions. This final product was then used to modify by drop casting the surface of a GCE (Fig. 3b). The developed electrochemical sensor was then applied for the selective and simultaneous detection of Cu²⁺, Cd²⁺, and Pb²⁺ in electrolyte solution, showing sensitivities of 1.30 µA µM⁻¹, 0.50 µA µM⁻¹, and 12.38 µA µM⁻¹, respectively, and LOD values near to the unit of µg L⁻¹ (parts per billion, ppb). These findings highlight the versatility of this analytical tool for ppb-level detection of heavy metals in complex environmental systems, including natural waters, sediments, and wastewater.

Indeed, MOFs have therefore emerged as one of the most versatile platforms for advancing electrochemical heavy-metal sensing. Their exceptional porosity, tailorable chemistry, and rich coordination environments enable efficient preconcentration and selective binding of target ions, even in complex matrices. When integrated with conductive substrates or transformed into MOF-derived materials, they overcome intrinsic limitations in electron transport and deliver robust analytical performance. In addition, MOF-based sensors offer a powerful route toward miniaturized, high-performance sensors capable of simultaneous multi-ion detection. Undoubtedly, continued progress in synthesis, functionalization, and device integration will further expand their applicability.

4. Microplastics and nanoplastics

Plastic materials have become indispensable to modern society. Their inertness, low cost, flexibility, and resistance to biodegradation, have led to their widespread use. The dependency of humans on plastics has escalated the use of plastic materials in several sectors over the last century. Every day, plastic products find various applications in human life, and can be easily seen and touched everywhere, but unfortunately, not only on supermarket shelves or in our homes. Millions of tonnes of plastic leak into the environment annually [74,75]. Indeed, plastic pollution is a significant environmental challenge worldwide, impacting oceans, rivers, soil, wildlife, and human health, with consequences that are only beginning to be understood. Nowadays, many countries worldwide have introduced regulations and policies to combat plastic pollution in marine systems, and in particularly micro- and nanoplastics. Micro- and nanoplastics are tiny plastic fragments formed from the breakdown of larger plastics or made small on purpose. Particularly,

microplastics are plastic fragments with dimensions lower than 5 mm [76], whereas nanoplastics are characterized by a preliminarily defined size range from 1 nm to 1 μm [77] and are usually derived from the degradation of raw plastics. These contaminants are raising concerns about their uptake and distribution within the biosphere and their potential ecological and toxicological impacts [78]. A schematic example of the potential toxic effect of microplastics on human health is shown in Fig. 4, considering plastic pollution in marine systems.

Currently, microplastics and nanoplastics are being characterized and detected using a multi-step workflow that combines microscopy (e.g., transmission electron microscopy (TEM), atomic force microscopy (AFM)), mass spectrometry (MS), thermal analysis, spectroscopy (Fourier-transform infrared (FTIR), Raman), and other methods, including pyrolysis coupled to gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (pyrolysis-GC-MS) [80,81]. Electrochemical sensors have also been proposed for microplastics detection [79], exploring different materials to improve sensors' selectivity and performance. Plastics is composed of a formulated polymer (i.e., polyethylterephthalate, polyethylene, polyvinyl chloride, polystyrene, polypropylene, polybutylene succinate, polylactic acid, etc.) to which selected additives (e.g., Bisphenol A, BPA) are added to give physical properties for several applications. Both polymers and additives can be detected. For examples, boron-doped diamond electrodes (BDDE) have been proposed for the determination of selected additives, based on the oxidation process of the target compounds (the selected additives) on the H-terminated-modified surface of the BDDE [82]. However, only a few examples of carbon and metal-based electrodes [83] are reported for microplastics detection [79] and are mainly focused on the determination of selected additives, often using electroanalytical techniques such as impedance spectroscopy or particle-impact electrochemistry [84–86].

Recently, MOFs and nanozymes have been highly investigated for plastic debris (microplastics and nanoplastics) removal. Indeed, MOFs have a large surface area and high porosity, and some publications are reported in the literature on their plastic debris adsorption capacity [87]. However, these studies on plastic removal by MOF materials are still in the early stages, with the mechanisms of interaction not always well described. Hydrophobic interaction seems important for plastic adsorption on MOFs as well as negative zeta-potentials of some polymers that offer good affinities with positively charged MOFs, such as 2D MOF@C@FeO and Cr-MOF [88]. Moreover, specific moieties on the microplastics and on MOF ligands can allow interaction by π - π stacking

and hydrogen bonding [89]. However, more knowledge on the interaction between plastic debris and MOFs and the study of environmental interference (e.g., pH and natural organic matters) are still necessary.

The surface area of MOFs has also been studied for sensing applications. A copper-centered metal-organic framework (Cu-MOF) film coupled with multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) was proposed for the determination of polystyrene (PS) nanoplastics [90]. The strategy exploited the redox properties of the exposed copper active sites within the Cu-MOF, further enhanced thanks to the presence of conductive MWCNTs. The resulting signal-off effect of nonconductive PS nanoplastics on the oxidation current of Cu^0 to Cu^+ was studied via linear sweep voltammetry. Reduced graphene oxide modified by cubic ZIF-8 (C-ZIF-8/rGO), was proposed by Liu *et al.* [91] for the determination of PS microplastics (PS-MP). The cubic ZIF-8 was synthesized via a cationic capping agent (CTAB) strategy to engineer a high surface positive charge density. This strategy facilitates electrostatic capture of negatively charged PS-MPs. Moreover, ZIF-8 was combined with rGO to enhance the electrical conductivity (Fig. 5a). Density functional theory (DFT) calculations were employed to elucidate the interfacial charge distribution and electron transfer mechanism between PS-MPs and C-ZIF-8/rGO, confirming that the enhanced positive surface charge of C-ZIF-8/rGO facilitates electron interaction with negatively charged PS.

MOFs have also demonstrated effectiveness in the degradation of microplastics and their resultant by-products [92]. Similarly, nanozymes with peroxidase-like activity, such as Fe_3O_4 nanoparticles, in the presence of H_2O_2 , can also catalyze microplastics degradation [74]. Recently, meso-macroporous N-doped carbon microspheres, with a high pyridinic nitrogen content and abundant oxygen vacancies, were proposed for the strong peroxidase-like activity [93]. These nanozymes, featuring charges opposite to those of nanoplastics, showed high adsorption capability for mixed nanoplastics, such as polyvinyl chloride, polystyrene, polyethylene terephthalate, and polymethyl methacrylate particles approximately 20 nm in size. Because of the aging phenomenon, these nanoplastics demonstrated excellent hydroxyl radical scavenging capacity. After nanoplastics adsorption, the pores and active sites of the nanozymes became filled and masked, thus resulting in a considerable decrease in their peroxidase-like activity. This loss of activity formed the basis of a nanozyme-based colorimetric sensor that exploits the differences in their aging phenomenon and adsorption capability. Recently, a Pt/graphdiyne/graphene (Pt/GDY/G) oxidase-like (OXD-like) nanozyme was studied for PS degradation [94].

Fig. 4. Schematic representation of the main sources, occurrence, and effects of microplastics in marine systems on marine organisms and humans. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [79].

Fig. 5. (a) Fabrication of C-ZIF-8/rGO and modification of the GCE surface for PS detection. Reproduced with permission from Ref. [91]. (b) Polystyrene degradation scheme proposed for Pt/GDY/G nanozymes. (i) Weight loss during polystyrene (PS) degradation over different catalysts. (ii) Degradation of PS by Pt/GDY/G at various pH values. (iii) TOC values in the residual solution at different reaction times. (iv–vi) SEM images of PS microplastics at different degradation times, with insets showing the water contact angle of the corresponding samples. XPS spectra of O 1s for (vii) undegraded polystyrene microspheres and (viii) degraded PS microspheres after 20 h. (ix) Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectra of PS microparticles at different degradation times. (x) Proposed pathway for PS degradation catalyzed by Pt/GDY/G. Adapted with permission from Ref. [94].

The interfacial electrostatic potential formed between GDY and platinum nanoparticles (Pt NPs) facilitates unidirectional electron transfer to the Pt site, establishing a first electronic ‘push effect’. Additionally, the sp-hybridized carbon (sp-C) sites in GDY serve as oxygen (O₂) adsorption centers, forming a sp-C-O-O-Pt bridge that facilitates electron transfer from GDY to O₂, creating a second electronic ‘push effect’. This dual electronic ‘push effect’ facilitates O₂ activation and O–O bond cleavage, resulting in a 3.4-fold increase in the OXD-like activity of Pt/GDY/G compared to Pt NPs, offering a promising strategy for the degradation of microplastics.

Despite the abovementioned advances in this field, a gap was observed in the literature: to the best of our knowledge, no electrochemical sensors that explicitly use nanozymes’ enzyme-like activity for micro- or nanoplastics detection have been reported to date.

5. Antibiotics monitoring with MOFs/nanozymes-enhanced sensors

The World Health Organization (WHO) has established a list of antibiotics that are important in human medicine and in veterinary practice. The top priority antimicrobials are cephalosporins, glycopeptides, macrolides and ketolides, polymyxins and quinolones [95]. Despite their importance in treating life-threatening infections, antibiotics also lead to a tension that has become increasingly hard to ignore. The same antibiotics onto which modern medicine relies are now persistently leaking into the environment, accumulating throughout the food chain as a result of their extensive and frequently careless usage in clinical settings, veterinary facilities, aquaculture, animal farming [7,96], and other activities. Thus, they can accelerate and spread antimicrobial resistance, one of the main challenges humanity will have to face in the near future in terms of public health and economy. Even though well established, accurate and sensitive analytical methods are available for antibiotics determination in environmental matrices, nowadays there is a growing demand for tools capable of tracking antibiotic residues on-site or in real time, especially in real-world contexts (e.g., aquaculture facilities, agriculture drainage, wastewater, etc.) where concentrations may

fluctuate rapidly. Electrochemical (bio)sensors respond to this need by combining practical benefits, such as simplicity of operation, low fabrication costs, and ease of integration in automatable instrumentation. In recent years, electrochemical platforms modified with MOFs and nanozymes have begun to appear in the literature regarding antibiotic monitoring [96]. A subset of these architectures is particularly relevant: those in which the MOF or nanozyme acts as both the recognition element and the signal generating component, rather than serving only as a passive support. These are the cases summarized in Table 2, which indicates the antibiotic target, the electrode material and the MOFs/-nanozymes used, the key mechanism followed to achieve the detection, the limit of detection reached, and whether the authors applied the sensor for real environmental samples or not.

Alongside these systems, in a parallel line of work some authors reported the integration of molecular recognition elements such as aptamers [97–99] or antibodies [100] coupled to MOFs or metallic nanomaterials (including nanozymes) for structure-specific recognition, using the nanostructure for signal generation.

6. Future perspectives

Electrochemical sensing plays a crucial role in environmental analysis, as it offers a combination of portability, low cost, rapid response, and compatibility with miniaturized devices. In this context, the introduction of innovative nanostructures and functional materials provides a useful strategy to strengthen selectivity and sensitivity of point-of-need systems. The convergence of electrochemistry with nanozyme and MOF engineering is poised to deliver the next generation of field-deployable sensors for reliable, real-time environmental monitoring (Table 3). Indeed, the recent literature has shown how these platforms are moving from proof-of-concept towards application-driven research or field-ready approaches, with more frequent attempts at real samples analysis and portable devices. However, to date, it seems that MOF/nanozyme-based technology is not yet fully ready for the transition to on-site, deployable formats and, while lab-scale performances are promising, the validation in real environments is lacking [111,112].

Table 2
Summary of sensing mechanisms and analytical performances of electrochemical sensors utilizing MOFs and/or nanozymes for antibiotic detection.

Target (s)	Primary MOF/nanozyme/material	Electrode material	Key mechanism	LOD	Real samples tested	Ref.
TAP	{[Zn ₃ (4,4'-bpy)(1,3,5-BTC) ₂ (DMPU) ₂ (H ₂ O) ₄] _n } (SXNU-1-Zn)	GCE	Zn atoms facilitated TAP reduction.	4.5 nM	Spiked tap water	[101]
CIP	Fe-based MOF as nanozyme, GDY/CNTs	GCE	Fe ³⁺ of Fe-MOF coordinates with the carbonyl and carboxyl groups of CIP, accelerating the Fenton reaction to enhance peroxide-like activity of Fe-MOF, which catalyzes o-phenylenediamine oxidation.	8.3 nM	n.a.	[102]
EF	Cu–Ni bimetallic-organic framework	GCE	Interaction between Cu ²⁺ of the MOF and pyridone and carboxylate moieties of the EF and electron transfer facilitated by Ni ²⁺ .	15.17 nM	River water	[103]
CIP, LEV, EF	Ce-based MOF synthesized using benzene-1,3,5-tricarboxylic acid	GCE	Ce ³⁺ /Ce ⁴⁺ centers facilitate analyte interaction and electron transfer for analyte oxidation.	0.11 μM CIP, 0.063 μM LEV, 0.047 μM EF	Water	[104]
TN	FeCoNi-MOF modified with carbon nanoparticles	GCE	The exposed bimetallic or trimetallic sites in the FeCoNi-MOF enhances its electrocatalytic performance toward TN reduction.	0.7 nM	Drug samples	[105]
CIP	Ni-MOF based on {[Ga ₂ (H ₂ TCPPO)(OH) ₂]-5DMF·2H ₂ O} _n	SPCE	Multiple type of interactions of the MOF and CIP, and the MOF acts as electrocatalyst for CIP oxidation.	145 μM	n.a.	[106]
NOR	Cu-shell Ag NPs encapsulated in CNTs grown on a MOF-derived carbon framework	GCE	Electrocatalyst toward NOR oxidation.	0.002 μM	Aquaculture water	[107]
GAT	Ni-MOF coupled to Ni nanorods	GCE	Electrocatalyst toward GAT oxidation.	0.0038 μM	River water	[108]
ODZ	MOF-derived Co-supported N-doped CNTs nanocomposite	GCE	Electrocatalytic oxidation of ODZ at the modified surface, which enhances electron transfer and adsorption.	6.7 nM	River water, tap water, fruit juice	[109]
MAT	Ni-MOF, β-cyclodextrin and functionalized carbon black	GCE	Electrocatalyst toward MAT reduction.	13.6 nM	River water	[110]

CIP: ciprofloxacin; CNTs: carbon nanotubes; DMF: *N,N*-dimethylformamide; DMPU: *N,N*-dimethylpropenylurea; EF: enrofloxacin; GAT: gatifloxacin; GCE: glassy carbon electrode; GDY: graphdiyne; LEV: levofloxacin; MAT: metronidazole; NOR: norfloxacin; NPs: nanoparticles; ODZ: ornidazole; SPCE: screen-printed carbon electrode; SXNU: Shanxi Normal University; TAP: thiamphenicol; TN: tinidazole.

Table 3

Summary of the main electrochemical techniques and MOF-related strategies and materials used in the literature for the various pollutant categories discussed.

Pollutant category	Primary electrochemical methods	Specific MOF strategies & materials	Key Bibliography refs.
PFAS (PFOA, PFOS)	EIS, DPV, CV	Fluorine-functionalized Cu-MOFs; 2D Conductive MOF thin films; MOF-nanozyme microchannel modulation.	[50–52]
Heavy Metals (Pb, Cd, Hg, etc.)	SWASV, DPASV, CV	MOF-Graphene Oxide nanocomposites; Ni-based MOFs; Hybrid MOF-Cellulose Nanocrystal-PEDOT: PSS.	[33,34,68,72,73]
Microplastics (MNPs)	Amperometry, Voltammetry, CV	Highly electroactive Cu-MOF films (unlabeled detection); MOF-based capture and removal systems.	[87,89,90]
Antibiotics	DPV, SWV, PEC, CV	Aptamer-MOF hybrids (Zr, Ag, Fe); Bimetallic MOFs (Cu–Ni, Cu@Ag); MOF-derived carbon nanocages.	[97,98,100,102,109]

Indeed, some questions remain open, including those about long-term stability, reproducibility [113], and regeneration of MOF/nanozyme electrodes in complex environmental matrices [111]. Strategies such as hydrophobic gating and MOF-on-MOF structures have been found to improve sensor stability, whereas their integration into digital tools seems to be a good compromise to further improve their performance. Hardware-based strategies can provide some help in improving data interpretation and reliability, for example, pairing with smartphone-linked potentiostats, and data acquisition and interpretation using artificial intelligence (AI). These devices filter out "matrix noise" (background signals from natural organic matter), allowing for a more accurate analyte quantification. In particular, as recently reported by Zhou *et al.* [114], AI and machine learning herald a new direction for smart detection systems once coupled with MOFs and similar porous materials in different ways: (i) predicting environmental events through the potential analytical capabilities of machine learning and AI in managing historical data and patterns; (ii) maintaining high data reliability within ever-changing environmental conditions, due to the self-calibration feature of these systems that allow automatically adjusting and optimizing detection parameters. However, conventional deep-learning models often do not offer insight into how decisions are made. Novel types of AI (*i.e.*, Explainable Artificial Intelligence) are claimed to overcome this limitation by bridging the gap between raw data and actionable knowledge.

Indeed, more systematic comparisons of MOF and nanozymes-based sensors against established analytical methods following rigorous validation using Certified Reference Materials are also needed for a complete transition to field operation.

7. Conclusions

In conclusion, MOFs and nanozymes have emerged as interesting materials applied to the development of sensors for environmental monitoring. These nanostructures can offer enhanced sensitivity and selectivity in detecting a wide array of pollutants. The modular nature of MOFs allows for precise structural tailoring, which is essential for identifying trace contaminants in complex matrices. Indeed, focusing on four main pollutant categories, this review discusses how the structural versatility of MOFs allows for the engineering of specific hydrophobic

sites for PFAS interaction, chelating sites for heavy metals, and size-selective pores for antibiotic detection. Furthermore, emerging research into MOF-based composites offers a promising route for the entrapment and identification of microplastics in aquatic matrices. Nanozymes and MOF-nanozyme composites enable signal amplification, improving the sensitivity and lowering detection limits of the related methodologies. These characteristics give these nanomaterials the potential to revolutionize field-deployable sensing technologies, providing robust solutions for real-time environmental protection and sustainable management. Nevertheless, the transition from controlled laboratory settings to the complexity of real samples may not be trivial. The next phase of this research will likely follow this path and seek further validation in real conditions and complex matrices.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Patrick Severin Sfragano: Writing – original draft, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Serena Laschi:** Writing – original draft, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Iliaria Palchetti:** Writing – original draft, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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